

INTERNET-MEDIATION AND THE INTERCULTURAL PERSPECTIVE IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The following article describes Internet-mediation and the Intercultural Perspective in Foreign Language Education. With the help of some teaching methods we can easily attract learner's attention and it gives us opportunity to develop their language ability.

When we first began work on this theme, it became clear to us that there was the potential for its purpose to be misconstrued as an explication of the use of technology and, more specifically, the Internet, in foreign language learning and teaching. This is a reasonable conclusion, of course, because the adjective “Internet-mediated” occurs in its title as a modifier of the phrase “foreign language education.” Such a perception might be supported further by the fact that an engagement with technology seems to permeate contemporary foreign language education with respect to pedagogy, curricular design, and research said Warschauer and Kern in their works The stated present-day preoccupation of FLE with technology is evidenced by the number of publications focusing on technology-related research and pedagogy in generalist journals in our field such as The Modern Language Journal and Applied Linguistics, the existence of

specialist journals devoted to issues of technology and language learning, the high number of conference presentations and symposia in which technology constitutes a key component, the ubiquity of required coursework on technology and language teaching in many graduate degree programs in the FLs and applied linguistics, as well as the sheer volume of recently coined terms and acronyms to index the intersection of technology and language learning. The attention paid to technology in FLE circles and in education in general is derivative of the attention that it attracts, for better or for worse, in other facets of modern life, where it has been heralded variously as the democratizing force par excellence; the hemlock of higher education; the new mediator of human identity and social activity; the death of meaningful human relations; one of the primary tools advancing socio-economic, linguistic, and cultural globalization; and

the medium that enables resistance to the crushing forces of global capital toward convergence. As pervasive and alluring as the role of technology in FLE might be, we do not view the adjective “Internet-mediated” to be the most important word in the title of this volume and, correspondingly, this volume is not primarily about the use of technology in FL learning and teaching. Instead, the emphasis for us lies on the adjective “intercultural” and the potential for FLE to serve as a site for the complexification of the self on linguistic, social, cultural, and ethical planes through lived experiences of communicative interaction with persons from other cultures in both additional and native languages. As a result, Internet-mediated intercultural foreign language education fundamentally is predicated on what Istvan Kecskes, in the inaugural editorial of *Intercultural Pragmatics*, refers to as the “intercultural perspective.” Language-related inquiry from the intercultural perspective takes the phenomenon of intercultural communication as its primary object of investigation. Intercultural communication differs from cross-cultural communication in that the latter “is usually considered a study of a particular idea or concept within several cultures that compares one culture to another on the aspect of interest, focuses on interactions among people from different cultures”. Scollon and Scollon further observe that intercultural communication involves “the study of distinct cultural or other groups in interaction with one another”. In the cross-cultural paradigm, on the other hand, “the members of the distinct groups do not interact with each other . . . but are studied as separate and separable entities”. There

are two analogies to be drawn here. The first regards the similarity of cross-cultural communication and traditional classroom-based FL instruction where learners study the language and the culture of a different group but typically do not interact with members of that group during instructional periods. The second analogy concerns the parallels between intercultural communication in general and ICFLE in particular where interaction with members of the studied internet-mediated intercultural Foreign language education and the intercultural speaker culture forms the leading classroom activity. Just as the intercultural perspective on communication brings “a multilingual angle into . . . overwhelmingly monolingual research paradigms,” directs special attention to the “dynamic nature of meaning and culture,” and investigates “the construction of culture by interactants with different national, ethnic, and racial backgrounds” , the linkage of different cultural groups in ICFLE shifts the focus of tutored FLE away from monolingual norms, static depictions of culture, and monolithic target-language identities toward the quotidian realities of multilingualism and the multiplicity of meaning and identity. As the above discussion makes clear, the hallmark of ICFLE, as defined in this volume, is the inclusion of living, breathing human representatives of the languages and cultures under study in classroom-based FL instruction. The Internet serves as the mediator of this inclusive process, but it is not the object of investigation per se; instead, it is the means by which educators may bring together those who represent various national, ethnic, socio-economic, social class, and faith-based viewpoints via

classroom practices generally termed “telecollaborative” in a supportive environment and in pedagogically sound ways to develop what has described as “intercultural competence” as well as grammatical and pragmatic FL competencies. To repeat a definition that by now has been learned by rote by many FL educators, particularly those who regard FLE as a curricular pillar of the humanistic tradition, Byram characterizes intercultural competence (IC) as “a readiness to suspend disbelief and judgment with respect to others’ meanings, beliefs and behaviours” and as a “willingness to suspend belief in one’s own meanings and behaviours, and to analyse them from the viewpoint of the others with whom one is engaging”. Byram likens this process to the ability to decenter, an advanced aspect of psychological development, which is necessary for understanding other cultures and may culminate in the dismantling of an individual’s “preceding structure of subjective reality and [its reconstruction] according to new norms” As is evident in this focus on culture, identity, behavior, and meaning, Byram does not view the development of FL linguistic competence as the sole or, indeed, as the most important outcome of FLE, although he does refer to such development as “central”. Instead, Byram argues that “the more desirable outcome is a learner with the ability to see and manage the relationships between themselves and their own cultural beliefs, behaviors and meanings . . . and those of their interlocutors. A person who possesses such abilities is referred to as an “intercultural” or sometimes “multicompetent” speaker, a pedagogy of the intercultural speaker in FL

classrooms would involve efforts to make classroom discourse itself more explicitly intercultural by identifying and examining the various social and cultural voices present in the class or by capitalizing on the multiple languages that may be present in the FL classroom. Kramersch further explains that “an increase in the quantity and quality of contacts between learners across national borders through student exchanges can result in a FL pedagogy wherein intercultural competence is fostered. Although Kramersch does not explicitly mention the role of Internet-mediated contacts in the implementation of an intercultural pedagogy, the essays in this volume amply demonstrate their potential to contribute to the goals of intercultural education, particularly for persons living in more culturally and ethnically homogenous regions, who may otherwise have limited opportunities to participate in prolonged intercultural communication. In ideologically monolingual cultures (see Train, this volume), where educational achievement is often measured in terms of the attainment of skills and the possession of facts and figures, there is the danger that the development of the interpretive expertise characteristic of the intercultural or multicompetent speaker may be underappreciated or, worse yet, overlooked as an educational and/or life goal. In such contexts, intercultural speakers may be misunderstood, devalued, marginalized, oppressed, or even despised, often by virtue of their membership in multiple communities, and as they move with artful poise and linguistic grace in the interstices and in the inlands of their own interpretive repertoires. Kramersch’s use of the word “privilege” to index the state of

being an intercultural speaker is an attempt to remedy this injustice, among other things. Individual Contributions to the Volume The chapters in this volume fall into three categories: 1) the pedagogy of ICFLE; 2) research on ICFLE; and 3) new developments in ICFLE. The volume is framed with opening and concluding chapters by Steven L. Thorne and Robert Train, respectively. In Chapter 1, which functions as a prologue, Thorne argues for the relevance of a shift from communicative competence to intercultural competence and outlines the role of ICFLE in this process. Aimed primarily at the concerns of FL instructors and language program directors, Thorne provides a detailed description of ICFLE pedagogical frameworks, a select review of research, and a discussion of the cultural variability of Internet communication tools used to mediate ICFLE partnerships. In Chapter 9, which serves as an epilogue, Train offers a critical appraisal of the ways in which key ideologies of FLE, such as the Native Speaker and the Native Standard Language, are either reproduced or challenged in the telecollaborative partnerships reported here. Concrete examples from each chapter are examined with a view to creating meta-discursive awareness of the ideologies and conceptual metaphors that underpin both research and practice in Internet-mediated intercultural foreign language education. Above and beyond this organizational taxonomy, the chapters in this volume can be distinguished according to whether or not they investigate primarily the development of intercultural or linguistic competence in telecollaboration., the primary emphasis lies on the development of intercultural competence. FL researchers

and practitioners, however, have also recognized the potential of telecollaborative instruction for the development of linguistic and/or pragmatic competence. Studies in this vein generally vary according to the ways in which the native-speaking keypals and the process of intercultural communication itself are conceptualized. In those studies that espouse the interactionist hypothesis as their guiding theoretical framework, the foreign partners typically are conceptualized as L2 “input providers,” while the action of Internet-mediated intercultural communication is seen as a costeffective means for learners to obtain exposure to comprehensible input that, in turn, can provide opportunities for the negotiation of ideational meaning and the subsequent acquisition of L2 structures. In contrast, the foreign partner is generally understood as a person embedded in particular socio-historical contexts and settings who exercises agency for specific, personally meaningful reasons, while the electronic interactions in which they engage are viewed as dynamic sites for the interpersonal construction and contestation of identity in and through language in those investigations that are underpinned by sociocultural, semiotic, or linguistically critical theoretical commitments. The contributions to this volume that focus on the ways in which ICFLE affords linguistic or pragmatic development, , span the range of theoretical possibilities described above. Bauer et al. provide an updated report on the Cultura Project, one of the most widely recognized and exemplary pedagogical projects incorporating telecollaborative practices for the purposes of ICFLE. Cultura is based on the premise that FL students

can and should develop critical perceptions of both their own as well as another's culture through the structured juxtaposition of texts and images, the creation and interrogation of lexical and semantic networks, and the sharing of interpretations of these data by participants in intercultural exchanges. The authors detail the development of the project since its start in French language courses at the Massachusetts Institute of Technology in 1997 to include new techniques and technologies, additional institutions, new topics and issues, and the instruction of less commonly taught languages. In particular, Bauer and her colleagues describe the adaptation of the principles and techniques of *Cultura* to two new socio-institutional settings: 1) a Russian-English exchange between intermediate students of English at the University of Petrozavodsk in Russia and second and third-year students of Russian at Brown University; and 2) a Spanish-English exchange between third-year students of English enrolled in a course called "Intercultural Comparisons" at the Universidad de las Américas in Puebla, Mexico, and third-year students of Spanish in a course on Hispanic Populations in the United States also at Brown University. While the Russian-American exchange illustrates the pressures of the digital divide and the operation of socioinstitutional constraints on the execution of a specific intercultural collaboration, the Mexican-American partnership highlights how a *Cultura*-based pedagogy can foster an increasingly complex sense of national identities and cultural heterogeneity in language learners. Because the authors focus explicitly on the challenges associated with the expansion of

the project to new institutions and languages, the chapter provides practical advice as well as instructional inspiration for FL teachers, language program directors, and other administrators who are contemplating involvement with ICFLE. Andreas Müller-Hartmann is also concerned with the development of intercultural competence via telecollaborative activity. His contribution to the volume is unique, however, in that it examines the potential of Internet-mediated intercultural language and culture learning partnerships to foster IC in pre- and in-service FL and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers rather than in language students. Relying on an empirically robust data set of five years of German-American telecollaborative exchanges between the Pädagogische Hochschule Heidelberg in Germany and The Pennsylvania State University in the United States, Müller-Hartmann demonstrates how the processes of reflective practice and model learning contribute to the construction of teacher knowledge bases with respect to critical media literacy, the design, execution, and management of international telecollaboration projects, and the development of intercultural competence via participation in such projects. Qualitative evidence for student-teachers' emerging knowledge bases in these areas is found in the pages of their cumulative course portfolios, in retrospective interviews and surveys, and in the micro-interactive details of their electronic interactions. Müller-Hartmann's description of his two-tiered instructional configuration involving a transatlantic pairing of two graduate-level teacher education/applied linguistics seminars, the

members of which observed and discussed the intercultural interactions of a second pair of undergraduate language courses as they engaged in telecollaborative activities, will be of particular interest to those language program directors who wish to integrate technology-enhanced experiential intercultural learning into their FL teacher education programs. Robert O'Dowd explores the use of "hands-on" ethnographic protocols by students in telecollaboration as a means of developing intercultural competence, including the operation of the skills of discovery in real time. Third-year English students at the University of Essen in Germany and undergraduate students in a Communication Studies course at the University of Columbus in Ohio received training in the use of typical ethnographic interviewing techniques such as descriptive or grand tour questions and creative listening. These techniques were later utilized by the same students in classroom-based interactions with their foreign keypals in the media of both e-mail and videoconferencing in order to construct thick descriptions of their keypals' culture from an emic, or insider's, perspective. O'Dowd's project is of import to the field of ICFLE because it is one of the few studies in which the influence of both text and image-based Internet communication tools is examined. In addition, the stipulation that project participants maintain an ethnographic stance in their intercultural interactions raises important questions about both the possibility and desirability of "objective talk" and "neutral observation" in intercultural communication, and their relationship to the development of critical cultural awareness. Drawing on richly

detailed excerpts from videoconference transcripts, the chapter provides practicing FL teachers with valuable information on the pedagogy of intercultural videoconferencing in FLE. Paola E. Dussias asks whether text-based, Internet-mediated intercultural communication has measurable consequences for the development of face-to-face oral communication. She compares two sets of L2 learners, all enrolled in fourth-semester university-level Spanish courses, but who were assigned to either an experimental group that engaged in an ICFLE partnership with native speakers in Spain or to a control group that also participated in Internet-mediated activity but with one another in intra-class electronic discussions. Both groups engaged in synchronous and asynchronous computer-mediated communication interaction. The focus of the study is a comparative linguistic analysis carried out on transcriptions of pre- and post-semester ACTFL Oral Proficiency Interviews. Her findings indicate that relative to learners in the control group, students in the experimental group demonstrated an increased capacity to attend to linguistic form, such as control over the use of overt-null subjects in Spanish, a finding that Dussias associates with awareness of NS discourse strategies made possible by the intercultural CMC discussions. Another student showed decreases in hesitations, pauses, and lexical interference from his L1. While expressing caution about generalizing these findings to other populations of learners, her conclusion is that the experimental group benefited from the interactions and that language learning mediated by the use of synchronous and asynchronous Internet communication

tools appears to readily transfer to spontaneous oral language production. The participants engaged one another using two tasks—an open-ended question and a goal-oriented activity. Confirming the results of other studies, Lee found that for both the NS and NNS groups, lexical rather than syntactical errors were the main triggers for negotiation moves. Differences between the groups included the proportional use of particular moves, in particular that the NS group exhibited the strong tendency to provide corrective feedback using recasts. The NS use of recasts was successful in focusing the NNSs' attention to errors in form as indicated by the high rate of NNS repairs. Lee notes that CMC provides a form of "written visual communication" that may

have also facilitated the NNS response to corrective feedback. Her conclusions are that NCI empowers learners to become active and effective language users, supports a variety of interaction types, and promotes negotiation of meaning. The topic for the exchange was to discuss two school shootings, one at Columbine High School in Littleton, Colorado, and the other in Germany at the Johannes Gutenberg Gymnasium in Erfurt. A significant conflict occurred during their interactions. In response, rather than proposing strategies to either deal with or avoid conflict, Schnieder and von der Emde report on the development of a dialogic paradigm that reframes the tensions of intercultural communication as valuable sites for intercultural exploration and learning.

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